

An Improved Model for Live Migration in Data Centre Simulators

Vincenzo De Maio*, Gabor Kecskemeti†, Radu Prodan*

*Institute of Computer Science, University of Innsbruck

*Dipartimento di Informatica, Università degli studi di Salerno

†MTA SZTAKI, Laboratory of Parallel and Distributed Systems

Email: {vincenzo,radu}@dps.uibk.ac.at, kecskemeti.gabor@sztaki.mta.hu

Abstract—Due to the difficulty of employing real data centres’ infrastructure for assessing the effectiveness of energy-aware algorithms, many researchers resort to use simulation tools. These tools require precise and detailed models for virtualized data centres in order to deliver accurate results. In recent years, many models have been proposed, but most of them either do not consider energy consumption related to virtual machine (VM) migration or do not investigate some of the energy impacting components (e.g. CPU, network, storage). We propose a new model for data centre energy consumption that takes into account the previously omitted components and provides more accurate energy consumption predictions compared to other state-of-the-art solutions. We evaluate our model’s accuracy in a comprehensive set of scenarios implemented in the combined GroudSim/DISSECT-CF simulator. Our analysis revealed a significant improvement in accuracy (up to 42.5%) in the modelled energy consumption compared to a similar state-of-the-art simulator.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, Cloud computing has emerged as a new paradigm by which computational power is hosted in data centres of specialised providers and rented on-demand to the users based on their occasional needs. Since power consumption has an increased significance for Cloud providers [1], they are more interested in optimising their data centre’s energy efficiency to maximise the profit. One way of improving the data centre energy efficiency is to maximise the utilisation of the *physical machines (PMs)*, which are often under-utilised according to the study in [2]. For this purpose, data centre operators often apply a technique called *workload consolidation* that increases the resource utilisation by mapping computational tasks on a subset of the data centre’s PMs and shutting down the rest (i.e. putting them in a low power state). Since computation is nowadays mostly running on *virtual machines (VMs)*, consolidation is the mapping of VMs to PMs.

Due to their energy efficiency benefits, a substantial amount of research has been invested on workload consolidation algorithms. However, due to the high cost of ownership and management expertise required to operate a real data centre, it is usually not possible for researchers to really use such a complex infrastructure to test the effectiveness of their algorithms. Therefore, there is a growing need for data centre infrastructure simulators offering a realistic environment for the evaluation of consolidation algorithms. Such simulators

need to model the behaviour and the energy consumption of each actor (e.g. PMs, VMs, routers/switches) and activity (e.g. VM migration, PM shutdown/startup) involved in the workload consolidation process. Amongst these activities, the most researched one is *VM migration*, which allows moving the state of VMs between PMs, useful for re-mapping VMs to PMs according to the data centre’s temporal needs.

In recent years, several simulators implemented models for VM migration. For example, the work in [3] added a model to the SimGrid [4] simulator that focuses on the migration’s performance overhead, but not on the energy consumption behind it. Other efforts like [5] provide limited models that, for example, consider only the CPU load or the network transfers. Despite the widespread use of VM migration, many simulators ignore its energy impact and omit modelling its effects on data centre’s performance. However, according to [6], using energy prediction models for VM migration decisions can lead to up 73.6% of energy savings. Moreover, according to [7], VM migration may bring an energy consumption overhead of at least 600 J for a single VM migration, with an available bandwidth of 100 Mbit s^{-1} . Since VM migrations in data centres are in the order of thousands per hour, this energy consumption component cannot be neglected. Therefore, adding an energy consumption model of VM migration is a significant improvement to the state-of-the-art in data centre simulations.

In this paper, we first propose a new energy consumption model to be used in data centre simulators that considers VM migration operations. Our new approach extends on our previous generic VM migration model [8] implemented in a Cloud infrastructure simulator called DISSECT-CF [9], and integrated as a back-end of the user-side GroudSim simulator [10]. Compared to other simulators, our model increases the simulation accuracy of VM migration and similar activities involved in the workload consolidation process. Our ultimate aim is to provide the research community with a model that is (1) easy to implement, and (2) able to capture the behaviour of different types of data centres components.

Our migration model is based on the assumption that the source (where the VM runs before consolidation) and the target (where the VM runs after consolidation) PMs are homogeneous. This assumption mimics the current state of most hypervisors (e.g. Xen, KVM) which prevent VM migration between PMs with incompatible architectures. Our model does

not consider energy consumption of network switches, proven to be constant in most cases and not related to the increased traffic caused by VM migrations, as shown in [11].

We validated our model by comparing it with real-life measurements from various benchmarks executed on VMs migrated across two different sets of PMs in a private Cloud. Our results managed to (1) improve the energy models of GroudSim/DISSECT-CF by means of piecewise linear regression, (2) validate our new model’s implementation under different operational scenarios with and without VM migration, and (3) achieve a 45.2% improvement in normalised modelling error compared to the state-of-the-art CloudSim simulator.

The paper is organised as follows. First, we review the related work in Section II. Then, we describe in Section III our new energy model and evaluate its accuracy in Section VI. We describe in Section V the implementation of our model in the GroudSim and DISSECT-CF simulators, and evaluate its performance and accuracy in Section VI. Finally, we conclude our paper in Section VII.

II. RELATED WORK

Several papers proposed models for data centre energy consumption, however, they either focus on a specific CPU architecture [12] or assume a linear relationship between CPU usage and energy consumption [13], leading to inaccurate results [14]. Many different works [6], [7] modelled the VM migration’s [15] energy consumption, but they consider neither the over-commitment nor the impact of different data centre actors on energy consumption [8]. Moreover, they have not yet been implemented in a Cloud simulator.

CloudSim [5] is the most widely used and cited simulator of different data centre infrastructure components, including internal networking and energy consumption. However, CloudSim assumes that the energy consumption exclusively depends on CPU utilisation by ignoring other components such as memory and network. Moreover, it does not take into account several important parameters in its VM migration model such as over-commitment and memory dirtying rate.

SimGrid [4] provides a scalable and fast simulation framework of cloud data centres, Grid and peer-to-peer systems, including a model for simulating VM migration [3]. However, while it models the energy consumption of PMs, it offers no energy consumption model for VM migration (at this time).

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GreenCloud [16] offers packet-level simulations for energy-aware Cloud computing data centres. It provides the capability of separately modelling the energy consumption of all data centre components, including CPU, network, and storage. However, its CPU model is limited to Xeon processors and provides no energy consumption model for live migration.

DCSim [17] provides fine-grained data centre simulation at

different levels of abstraction considering networking and energy consumption models, with no support for VM migration.

Our work is based on the GroudSim [10] simulation backend of the ASKALON system [18] that, due to its integration with the DISSECT-CF [19] Cloud infrastructure simulator, provides models for energy consumption of many data centre components, including VM migration and networking.

III. MODEL

In this section, we describe the generic computation-oriented (e.g., excluding air conditioning) data centre energy consumption model underneath our approach, derived from our previous study in [8]. We designed our model by first making it able to predict the instantaneous power draw of a server in a data centre, and then extending it with a model for live VM migration (starting with Section V-C). Our model considers CPU utilisation as the main parameter of PMs, for which it extracts a regression model. Although CPU is the most impacting factor according to [20], we also consider network transfers and disk operations to improve accuracy over existing models (that usually do not consider them), as they play a crucial role in the migration process.

The computation-oriented energy consumption of a data centre E_d is the integral of its instantaneous power draw $P_d(t)$:

$$E_d = \int_{t_{start}}^{t_{end}} P_d(t) dt, \quad (1)$$

where $[t_{start}, t_{end}]$ is the interval for which we calculate the energy consumption, and $P_d(t)$ is the sum of instantaneous power draw $P(h, t)$ of each PM h at the time instance t :

$$P_d(t) = \sum_{\forall h \in \mathcal{H}} P(h, t), \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{H} is the set of all PMs in the data centre.

The instantaneous power consumption of a PM is the sum of the power draw of its hardware components. While the power draw of some components (e.g. memory, PCI slots, motherboard) is constant over time, some others (e.g. CPU, network, disk) vary depending on their load, for which we distinguish two idle and active parts:

$$P(h, t) = P_{idle}(h, t) + P_{active}(h, t). \quad (3)$$

The idle power $P_{idle}(h, t)$ is a constant representing the power drawn to keep the machine ready (i.e. turned on). The active power $P_{active}(h, t)$ is instead dependent on the load of the PM’s hardware components and its value lies in the interval $[0, P_r(h)]$, where $P_r(h) = P_{max}(h) - P_{idle}(h)$ and $P_{max}(h)$ is the maximum power draw of the PM h . For simplicity, we assume that P_{active} is influenced mostly by the CPU, network transfers and I/O operations such read/write on disk, as demonstrated in [21]:

$$P_{active}(h, t) = P_{cpu}(h, t) + P_{net}(h, t) + P_{io}(h, t). \quad (4)$$

We analyse each component of the active power in the following subsections.

Fig. 1: Instantaneous power draw of a PM in relation to CPU utilization.

A. PM load model

As active power is dependent on the load, before we can model the power, we provide models for characterising the load behaviour of PMs. We calculate the load of CPU components as follows:

$$load_{cpu}(h, t) = \frac{CPU(h, t)}{CPU^{max}(h)}, \quad (5)$$

where $CPU^{max}(h)$ is the maximum CPU load on PM h and $CPU(h, t)$ is its load h at time instance t . Then, we define the network load as a measure of how much data are sent/received over the network at the time instance t on PM h :

$$load_{net}(h, t) = \frac{BW_{net}(h, t)}{BW_{net}^{max}(h)}, \quad (6)$$

where $BW_{net}^{max}(h)$ is the maximum bandwidth on the network interface of PM h and $BW_{net}(h, t)$ is the bandwidth used at time instance t . Finally, we define the disk load as a measure of the amount of bytes written at time instance t on PM h :

$$load_{disk}(h, t) = \frac{BW_{disk}(h, t)}{BW_{disk}^{max}(h)}, \quad (7)$$

where $BW_{disk}^{max}(h)$ is the maximum disk bandwidth on the PM h and $BW_{disk}(h, t)$ is the bandwidth at time instance t .

B. CPU power model

As CPU is the most influential component on the energy consumption of a PM [20], we focus mostly on its modelling. Most works on CPU energy modelling [22], [23] assume a linear relationship between the CPU load and its effect on power draw. However, CPU power draw is more aligned with a piecewise linear trend according to our observations in Figure 1 using the two machines presented in Table I. The initial transition from idle to non-idle state, when several hardware components are simultaneously starting to draw power (e.g. caches), causes a higher growth in power draw at low load levels. Once all components are started, the power

grows at a different trend:

$$P_{low-cpu}(h, t) = \alpha(h) \cdot P_r(h) \cdot load_{cpu}(h, t) \quad (8)$$

$$P_{high-cpu}(h, t) = \beta(h) \cdot P_r(h) + (1 - \beta(h)) \cdot P_r(h) \cdot load_{cpu}(h, t);$$

$$P_{cpu}(h, t) = \begin{cases} P_{low-cpu}(h, t), & load_{cpu}(h, t) \leq \mathcal{L}(h); \\ P_{high-cpu}(h, t), & load_{cpu}(h, t) > \mathcal{L}(h); \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where $P_r(h) = P_{max}(h) - P_{idle}(h)$, $\mathcal{L}(h)$ is the load at which the trend changes on PM h , $load_{cpu}(h, t)$ is the CPU load on PM h at time instance t , $P_{max}(h)$ and $P_{idle}(h)$ are the maximum and idle power draw of PM h , and $\alpha(h)$ and $\beta(h)$ are the coefficients for low (i.e. $\leq \mathcal{L}(h)$) and high (i.e. $> \mathcal{L}(h)$) CPU load levels.

C. Network and storage models

For both network and I/O energy consumption, we assume a linear relationship between load and power draw. For the network, we extend on our previous work [24], while for the I/O we slightly simplify the model proposed in [21]. We consider in our simplified model only write operations because (1) they are more energy consuming [21] and (2) they occur more often in the live migration process, as explained in Section V-C). Therefore, we assume for both a linear relationship with the bandwidth:

$$P_{net}(h, t) = \gamma(h) \cdot P_r(h) \cdot load_{net}(h, t); \quad (10)$$

$$P_{disk}(h, t) = \delta(h) \cdot P_r(h) \cdot load_{disk}(h, t), \quad (11)$$

where $\gamma(h)$ and $\delta(h)$ are the model coefficients. In the next section, we evaluate the accuracy of our model.

IV. MODEL EVALUATION

A. Experimental setup

The experimental setup for training and validating our model presented in Section III employs two sets of machines summarised in Table I, both running the Xen hypervisor. We excluded these machines from the Cloud infrastructure for the time of these experiments. We used two external Voltech PM1000+ (<http://www.voltech.com/Support/Forum/tabid/151/forumid/5/scope/threads>) power measurement devices connected to the alternating current side of the machines, measuring their instantaneous power draw at a frequency of 2 Hz. We collected our measurements while the PMs were running a different number of VMs to mimic the behaviour of a modern virtual data centre. The VMs execute different kinds of CPU and memory-intensive workloads using the benchmarks introduced in [8]. To collect statistics about the CPU, network and storage load, we used the Xentop utility running on the dom-0 of both PMs. Since the minimum sampling frequency of Xentop is 1 Hz, we employed linear interpolation to obtain the missing resource utilisation values that accompany the more frequent data acquired from the power meters.

Machine	Available virtual CPUs	Available RAM	Gigabit NIC	Gigabit switch
m0x	32 (8 Opteron 8356,	32GB	Broadcom	Cisco Catalyst
o1x	40 (20 Xeon E5-2690,	128GB	Intel	HP

TABLE I: Experimental hardware configuration.

Model	PM set	\mathcal{L}	α	β	γ	δ	P_{idle} [W]	P_{max} [W]	MAE [W]	NRMSE [%]
Piecewise	m0x	0.12	5.29	0.68	0.05	0.1	501	840	18.28	6.2
	o1x	0.12	4.33	0.47	0.05	0.1	164	382	11.5	6.8
Linear	m0x		284.974	618.67					47.8	15.6
	o1x		165.08	212.563					23.7	13.9
Cubic	m0x		209.317	695.684					69.2	23.6
	o1x		140.753	235.776					37.3	20.4

TABLE II: Model coefficients and errors.

B. Regression modelling

We obtained $P_{idle}(h)$ and $P_{max}(h)$ by measuring the idle and maximum power draw with our power measurement devices, and the $\alpha(h)$ and $\beta(h)$ coefficients by using the CubiST (<https://www.rulequest.com/cubist-info.html>) tool. We selected this tool because it generates rule-based regression models with respect to the model designed for CPU power draw from Equation 9. We chose a subset of 20% from our measurements as the training set, and the rest for validation and evaluation using two error metrics: mean absolute error (MAE) and normalised root mean square error (NRMSE). To achieve a better accuracy, we employ the 10-fold cross-validation provided by the CubiST tool.

The validation results in Table II using a test set of 80% of our measurements show a NRMSE below 7% for both data sets, with an average MAE of 18.28 W on the $\{m01, m02\}$ machines, and of 11.5 W on the $\{o1, o2\}$ machines. We also compared our piecewise linear prediction with the linear model from [4] showing a reduction in NRMSE of 9.4% (15.6% versus 6.2%) on $\{m01, m02\}$ machines and of 7.1% (13.9% versus 6.8%) on $\{o1, o2\}$ machines. The improvement is even higher compared with the cubic model in [16], with a reduction in NRMSE of 17.4% (23.6% versus 6.2%) on the $\{m01, m02\}$ machines and of 13.6% (20.4% versus 6.8%) on $\{o1, o2\}$.

V. SIMULATION FRAMEWORK

In this section, we describe the simulation framework in which we implement our models consisting of two main parts: GroudSim that provides the user side of the IaaS Cloud, and DISSECT-CF that provides the internal infrastructure side.

A. GroudSim

GroudSim is a Java-based simulation toolkit for scientific applications running on Grid and Cloud infrastructures. GroudSim uses a discrete-event simulation toolkit consisting of a future event list and a time advance algorithm that offers improved performance and scalability compared to other process-based approaches [5]. The simulation framework supports modelling of Grid and Cloud computational and network resources, job submissions, file transfers, as well as

Fig. 2: DISSECT-CF architecture.

Fig. 3: Interaction between GroudSim and DISSECT-CF.

integration of failure, background load, and cost models. An advanced textual and visual tracing mechanism and a library-independent distribution factory give extension possibilities to the simulator. New tracing mechanisms can be easily added by implementing new handlers or filters in the event system, and additional distribution functions can be included by writing an appropriate adapter. GroudSim focuses on the user-side of IaaS Cloud computing and is currently used as an additional back-end in the ASKALON system, enabling users to perform development, debugging, simulation and execution of Grid and Cloud applications using the same interface [18].

B. DISSECT-CF

The main issue with GroudSim is that it lacks knowledge of the internal infrastructure. For this reason, we integrated it with DISSECT-CF, an open source Cloud simulator with special focus on the data centre infrastructure. Figure 2 summarises the DISSECT-CF architecture with its five major subsystems:

- *Event system* for providing a unified time reference;
- *Unified resource sharing* for modelling the sharing of the data centre resources;
- *Energy modelling* for simulating energy usage patterns of individual components (i.e. CPU, network, storage);
- *Infrastructure simulation* for modelling IaaS components, such as PMs, VMs and network entities;
- *Infrastructure management* encapsulating scheduling and other functionalities (e.g. VM instantiation, PM startup/shutdown) typical to real-world Clouds.

In this work, we mostly focus on three components: energy modelling, unified resource sharing, and infrastructure simulation, briefly outlined in the following subsections.

C. VM migration model

In our work, we aim at simulating not only the power draw but also the VM migration time. VM migration is the process of transferring the VM state from a *source* PM to another *target* PM. Usually, two types of VM migration are performed: *non-live* and *live migration*. In non-live migration, the VM is first suspended on the source PM, then its state is transferred to the target PM, and finally is resumed there. In live migration, the VM state is transferred while the VM is still running on the source PM. In [8], we identified three phases for both migration types:

- *Initiation phase*, during which the source PM prepares transferring the VM state to the target PM and the target reserves the resources necessary to PM the VM;
- *Transfer phase*, during which the VM state is transferred from the source to the target PM in a way depending on whether a non-live or live migration is performed;
- *Activation phase*, during which the source PM frees the resources occupied by the VM and the target starts it.

We therefore define the *VM migration time* $T_{migr}(v, h, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T})$ on PM h for migrating the VM v from the source \mathcal{S} to the target PM \mathcal{T} as the sum of the times required in each phase:

$$T_{migr}(v, h, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T}) = T_{init}(v, h) + T_{transf}(v, h, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T}) + T_{activ}(v, h). \quad (12)$$

In the initiation phase, the source PM prepares a checkpoint of the VM to be sent to the target. In the activation phase, the source PM frees the resource allocated to the VM and the target starts it. Therefore, the times required by both initiation $T_{init}(v, h)$ and activation $T_{activ}(v, h)$ phases depend only on the size of the VM's memory $SIZE(v)$ and the I/O bandwidth on the PM h :

$$T_{init}(v, h) = T_{activ}(v, h) = \frac{SIZE(v)}{BW_{io}(h)}. \quad (13)$$

In this equation h can represent both source and target PMs, since the time will be the same on both PMs. The transfer phase, on the other hand, has a different execution time for a live or a non-live migration. The non-live migration time $T_{transf}^{nonlive}$ depends only on the VM size and the mean available bandwidth $BW_{net}(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T})$ between the two PMs during the migration process:

$$T_{transf}^{nonlive} = \frac{SIZE(v)}{BW_{net}(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T})}. \quad (14)$$

Live migration is instead performed iteratively while the VM v is still running. Therefore, the VM state needs to be continuously updated over a predefined number of iterations set in the hypervisor configuration. After the initial state transfer, only the memory pages that have been modified are transferred in each iteration, leading to the following live VM transfer time:

$$T_{transf}^{live} = \frac{SIZE(v)}{BW_{net}(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T})} + \sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{I}} \frac{DP(v, i)}{BW_{net}(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T})}, \quad (15)$$

where \mathcal{I} is the number of iterations and:

$$DP(v, i) = \frac{SIZE(v)}{PS(v)} \cdot DR(v, i), \quad (16)$$

where $DP(v, i)$ is the number of dirty pages at the iteration i and $DR(v, i)$ is the dirtying rate of the VM v (the percentage of memory pages marked as dirty during an iteration i), and $PS(v)$ is the size of each memory page of VM v .

D. Energy simulation

This section describes the design and implementation of our energy model in the DISSECT-CF infrastructure simulator [9] and integrated in the user-oriented GroudSim simulator [19].

1) *Energy modelling*: In this module, we extended the `ConsumptionModel` class with two subclasses (`CPUConsumptionModel` and `LinearConsumptionModel`) that model the instantaneous power draw according to the Equations 9 and 11. The $\alpha(h)$ and $\beta(h)$ parameters, the idle P_{idle} and the maximum P_{max} power draw, as well as the $\mathcal{L}(h)$ parameter from Equation 9 are set by the user when configuring the simulation. From the combination of these parameters, we obtain the CPU's power draw function $P_{cpu}(h, t)$. Similarly, the $\gamma(h)$ and $\delta(h)$ parameters in Equation 11 define the network $P_{net}(h, t)$ and disk $P_{disk}(h, t)$ power draw functions. Each class provides an `evaluateConsumption(load)` method which, when queried, gives the instantaneous power draw of each particular component (e.g. CPU, network, I/O) according to the instantaneous `load` parameter modelled using the Equations 5, 6 and 7.

2) *Unified resource sharing*: In this module, we added support for tasks consuming not only CPU, but also memory resources. This is especially important for live migration, since its time and energy consumption are influenced by the way the memory is used. In [8], we identified the memory dirtying ratio – $DR(v, i)$ – as one of the most influential parameters on VM live migration's energy consumption. To support its simulation, we extended the `ResourceConsumption` class to allow users to specify the number of memory pages used by a task and its memory dirtying rate. If no dirtying rate is specified during task creation, we consider the task as not modifying its memory pages during execution.

3) *Infrastructure simulation*: We based the extension of this module on our previous studies performed in [8]. To add live VM migration capabilities to DISSECT-CF, we extended both `VirtualMachine` and `PhysicalMachine` classes. In the `VirtualMachine` class, we added methods that allow the simulation of live migration in six steps.

a) *Initial state transfer*: The first step of live VM migration is moving the actual state of the VM to the target PM without suspending the VM. For this, the hypervisor creates a memory image of the migrating VM and sends it to the target PM. We simulate this in multiple steps. First, we allocate a matching resource set for the VM on the target PM. If the allocation succeeds, we create a *storage object* of the same VM memory size and simulate its transfer using plain TCP.

b) *Continuous update*: Since the VM is still running, its state in memory may be modified during its transfer to the target PM. To have a consistent image on the target, we need to transfer these modifications too, requiring multiple transfers before reaching a consistent state on the target. Xen terminology names each transfer as `pre-copy round` consisting of two steps:

- 1) *Identify changes in the VM's state and transfer them to the target PM* In real-life, the hypervisor monitors these changes by marking memory pages as dirty if they have been modified by the VM (v) since the initial transfer or the last update. In the simulator, we calculate the amount of dirtied pages called *written working set (WWS)* by using the memory dirtying rate parameter defined in Section V-D2 in the `identifyWWS()` method:

$$WWS(v) = DR(v) \cdot \Delta t, \quad (17)$$

where $DR(v)$ is the dirtying rate (typical amount of pages dirtied in a second) and Δt is the time since the initial transfer or last update. The `identifyWWS()` method returns a storage object of the size of the WWS.

- 2) *Update the state of target PM with modifications occurred in the source during state transfer* Once we identify the WWS, we transfer it to the target PM, similarly as in the initial transfer step.

In real-life, the hypervisor performs this phase until a termination criterion is reached (otherwise the migration could never terminate). In the simulator, we employ the same termination criteria used in Xen's live migration [15]: (1) $WWS \leq 256 \text{ KiB}$ or (2) the maximum number of pre-copy rounds is reached. We calculated this number at runtime based on the available bandwidth.

c) *Suspend the VM*: Once the pre-copy phase finishes, VM is suspended to allow transferring its last state modifications to the target PM. For this, our simulation suspends each task running on the VM using the `ResourceConsumption.suspend()` method, and then sends the modifications performed since the last pre-copy round to the target PM, similar to the pre-copy phase.

d) *Resume the VM on the target*: If no error occurred until this point, the state of the VM on the target PM is coherent with the source PM. Therefore, we resume the tasks suspended in the previous state so that the VM is effectively running on the target PM.

e) *Destroy the VM on source*: After the new VM is resumed, we can finally free the resources previously owned by the VM on the source PM using the `release()` method on the VM's resource allocation at the source PM.

E. GroudSim and DISSECT-CF interaction

Figure 3 displays how to obtain DISSECT-CF energy readings in GroudSim. To measure the energy consumption in a data centre, we need two basic information: the PMs and their load. Energy consumption can be monitored through the *IaaS Service* of DISSECT-CF which is responsible for both instantiating and maintaining the data centre infrastructure, as well as

for allocating a VM to a suitable PM. For this purpose, the IaaS Service meter attaches an `EnergyMeter` to each PM defined in the data centre. For each PM, we define a piecewise linear `ConsumptionModel` for CPU, network and storage that determines the instantaneous power draw of each component, as discussed in Section V-D1. The energy meters collect these instantaneous power estimates with a user-defined frequency and calculate the energy consumption based on the simulated time spent since the last power measurement. At the end of the simulation, the IaaS service's meter aggregates the energy consumption for the entire data centre.

VI. EVALUATION

We evaluate our energy model for VM migrations by first introducing our benchmarks and the experimental testbed. Then, we describe how we simulate the execution of these benchmarks on top of the combined GroudSim/DISSECT-CF simulator. Finally, we compare our simulation results with energy traces collected from real executions.

A. Benchmarks

We employ the benchmarks designed in [8] to validate the implementation of our new VM migration model in the DISSECT-CF simulator because (1) they already proved their effectiveness in testing our VM migration model, and (2) they allow checking the accuracy of the CPU, network and disk models by varying the CPU load and the dirtying rate, which are the parameters that mostly affect the VM migration. We describe these benchmarks in the following subsections (see Tables III and IV).

1) *CPULOAD*: We investigate the impact of VM workload on live and non-live migration with two types of experiments:

a) *CPULOAD-SOURCE*: investigates the impact of CPU-intensive workloads running on the source PM by migrating a VM to an idle target PM. The load of the source is progressively increased from idle to 100% CPU utilisation to quantify its impact on VM migration. We also consider the case of over-commitment in which the VMs require more CPUs than the PM can offer to ensure multiplexing amongst them.

b) *CPULOAD-TARGET*: investigates the impact of CPU-intensive workloads running on the target PM by migrating a VM from a source PM running the VM only. The load of the target is progressively increased from idle to 100% CPU utilisation to quantify its impact. In this experiment, we also consider the effects of multiplexing on hardware resources.

2) *MEMLOAD*: experiments study the effect of varying the dirtying rate of the workload on the VM migration. We designed the following experiments to compare the impact of memory-intensive workloads with CPU-intensive ones running on both source and target PMs:

a) *MEMLOAD-VM*: studies the impact of memory-intensive workloads by increasing the percentage of memory pages dirtied in the migrating VM. The source PM is running the migrating VM only and the target is idle. This experiment serves as a baseline for the following two.

Experiment	Source PM configuration		Target PM configuration		Migrating VM configuration		
	CPU	Memory	CPU	Memory	Instance	CPU	Memory
CPULOAD-SOURCE	[0 – 100]%	5%	idle	5%	migrating-cpu	100%	5%
CPULOAD-TARGET	1xmigrating-cpu	5%	[0 – 100]%	5%	migrating-cpu	100%	5%
MEMLOAD-VM	idle	5%	idle	5%	migrating-mem	100%	[5 – 95]%
MEMLOAD-SOURCE	[0 – 100]%	5%	idle	5%	migrating-mem	100%	95%
MEMLOAD-TARGET	1xmigrating-mem	5%	[0 – 100]%	5%	migrating-mem	100%	95%

TABLE III: Experimental design.

ID	Virtual CPUs	Linux kernel	RAM	Workload	Storage size
load-cpu	4	2.6.32	512 MB	matrixmult	1 GB
migrating-cpu	4	2.6.32	4 MB	matrixmult	6 GB
migrating-mem	1	2.6.32	4 MB	pagedirtier	6 GB
dom-0	1	3.11.4	512 MB	VMM	115 GB

TABLE IV: Experimental VM configurations.

b) *MEMLOAD-SOURCE*: investigates how live migration is impacted by: (1) CPU-intensive workloads running on the source PMs and (2) memory-intensive workloads running on the migrating VM. We perform a live migration of a VM running a memory-intensive workload from a source PM running a CPU-intensive workload with increasing utilisation on an idle target.

c) *MEMLOAD-TARGET*: investigates how live migration is impacted by: (1) CPU-intensive workloads running on the target PM and (2) memory-intensive workloads running on the migrating VM. We perform a live migration of a VM running a memory-intensive workload to a target PM running a CPU-intensive workload with increasing utilisation. The source PM is running the migrating VM only.

We summarise the hardware and software configuration of our benchmarks in Table III. We describe in Table IV the VM instances employed in our experiments, as well as the application used for generating the CPU and memory-intensive workloads. *matrixmult* is a simple OpenMP matrix multiplication kernel that models CPU-intensive workloads, while *pagedirtier* is a plain ANSI C program that continuously writes the memory pages allocated to the VM in random order. We execute each experiment on both sets of machines described in Table I running the Xen 4.2.5 hypervisor. We attach to each PM an external Voltech PM1000+ power reader, as already discussed in Section IV and collected the measurements during the execution of our benchmarks. For each experimental run, we start the measurement after deploying the VM on the PM, issue the migration once the power draw of the PM stabilises, and end the measurement once the power trace stabilises (meaning that we obtain twenty consecutive power measurements with a difference lower than 0.3%, which is below our measurement device’s accuracy).

B. Benchmarks simulation

We implemented these benchmarks on top of DISSECT-CF to evaluate the accuracy of our simulations compared to the real measurements. We configured a simulated data centre only containing the relevant PMs from University of Innsbruck’s

Host	MAE-NONLIVE		NRMSE-NONLIVE		MAE-LIVE		NRMSE-LIVE	
	Power [W]	Energy [J]	Power [%]	Energy [%]	Power [W]	Energy [J]	Power [%]	Energy [%]
m01	42.97	4292.9	16.6	16.9	38.45	5345.8	15.5	8.1
m02	51.97	4179.5	18.3	15.1	67.33	6341.8	22	9.3
o1	11.98	2248.6	8.2	14.6	27.6	3375.5	18.4	11
o2	18.19	2417	14.6	13.2	48.1	5518	14.2	25.6

TABLE V: Simulation error for both machine set.

DPS cloud. These PMs matched the configuration of the two types of machines used during the regression modelling in Section IV. We simulated the load by deploying VMs on the PMs and configured each VM to have 4 GB of memory to resemble the configuration used to build our traces. To simulate the execution of our benchmarks, we assigned to each VM computing tasks resembling the execution of the selected workloads. We simulated the execution of *matrixmult* by assigning to the VM a computing task with full CPU utilisation and a memory dirtying rate of 0.05%, as measured over the execution of the real benchmark. In this case, we simulate the increasing load on the PM by increasing the number of VMs allocated to the PMs. Concerning *pagedirtier*, we also set the full CPU utilisation, but vary the memory dirtying rate for each experimental run, as indicated in Table III. For the non-live migration, we only vary the CPU load since the dirtying rate has no impact on it.

C. Simulation results

In the following, we compare the results obtained from our simulator with the power traces measured from the real execution of the aforementioned benchmarks. For this, we compute the MAE and NRMSE error metrics on both instantaneous power draw and energy consumption on both sets of machines. The results are summarised in Table V for both machine sets. We also compare in Figure 4 (for the (m01, m02) set) and Figure 5 (for the (o1, o2) set) the power traces obtained from our simulator with the real measurements. In each chart, we refer to the real measurements with a label starting with the ‘‘Real-’’ prefix to distinguish them from the simulated results marked with the ‘‘Dissect-’’ prefix. In each chart, we also distinguish between measurements taken on the source and target PMs using the ‘‘-SRC’’ and ‘‘-TRG’’ suffixes. Each measurement point is traced every 500 ms according to the power measurement devices’ resolution. We average each power reading over ten benchmark runs to ensure statistical significance. We show the consecutive execution of CPULOAD-SOURCE

(a) Non-live migration source.

(b) Non-live migration target.

(c) Live migration source.

(d) Live migration target.

Fig. 4: Simulated versus measured power draw traces for the (m01, m02) machine set.

and CPULOAD-TARGET benchmarks for the non-live instantaneous power draw traces, and the consecutive execution of CPULOAD-SOURCE, MEMLOAD-VM, CPULOAD-TARGET, MEMLOAD-SOURCE, and MEMLOAD-TARGET for the live migration traces.

We observe that our simulation is able to provide power values with a MAE not higher than 67.3 W compared to the

(a) Non-live migration source.

(b) Non-live migration target.

(c) Live migration source.

(d) Live migration target.

Fig. 5: Simulated versus measured power draw traces for the (o1, o2) machine set.

real measurements. This value is, however, influenced by the fact that the power draw is in some cases underestimated by around 100 W, like in Figure 4a (between 12 and 24 min) and Figure 4b (between 0 and 14 min), because the test scenarios active during these periods perform non-live migrations while both PMs are idle. In these situations, the simulator only considers the power draw caused by the network and storage

(and the idle CPU consumption), despite some slight CPU load caused by these two operations. This slight load leads to significant offsets in the power draw model according to the Figure 1. In future work, we will aim at modelling this CPU load in a generic way to increase the accuracy of the simulator in these unlikely test scenarios too. Nevertheless, NRMSE is in each case between 8% and 22% for instantaneous power draw, and between 8% and 25% for energy consumption (see Table V), showing that our simulator is able to predict both of them with a good accuracy.

D. CloudSim comparison

The goal of this section is to compare our simulation results with other simulators that use a piecewise linear model for energy consumption to ensure a fair comparison to our work, allowing simulations of different kinds of architectures. For this purpose, we compare our results with CloudSim [5], the most cited and widely used simulator in the community, employing a piecewise model [25] for power draw. We did not include DCSim [17] in our evaluation since it does not provide VM migration support at the time of writing required for a fair comparison. We further did not select SimGrid [4] despite its support for live migration [3] since it uses a linear model for energy consumption (http://simgrid.gforge.inria.fr/simgrid/3.12/doc/group__SURF__plugin__energy.html#ga166ef80adc810f0990d13539ddfd8adc). Finally, we did not select GreenCloud [16] because it employs a cubic model. We showed in Section IV-B that the linear and cubic models are highly inaccurate for our testbed (see Table II).

1) *Experimental setup:* To perform our comparison, with CloudSim, we implemented the same benchmarks used during our model validation in Section VI-A. We initialised a CloudSim simulation with a data centre consisting of two PMs with the same specifications as in Table I.

a) *Energy modelling:* CloudSim employs a piecewise linear energy model. For each type of CPU used in the simulation, the user needs to specify an array p with 11 power values, corresponding to the power draw at different CPU utilisation level, starting from idle to 100% in steps of 10. Based on these CPU utilisation levels, the power draw of a PM h at a given time instance is given by:

$$P(h, t) = p \left[\lfloor \text{load}_{cpu}(h, t) \cdot 10 \rfloor \right] + \delta \cdot \text{load}_{cpu}(h, t) - \frac{\lfloor \text{load}_{cpu}(h, t) \rfloor}{10} \cdot 100, \quad (18)$$

where: $\delta = \frac{p[\lfloor \text{load}_{cpu}(h, t) \cdot 10 \rfloor] - p[\lfloor \text{load}_{cpu}(h, t) \rfloor]}{10}$ and $\text{load}_{cpu}(h, t)$ is the CPU utilisation of PM h at time instance t as in Equation 9. This model is implemented in CloudSim by the `PowerSpecModelPower` class which we extended to model the two CPU types used.

b) *Benchmark simulation:* Applications running on VMs are modelled in CloudSim by instances of the `CloudLet` object configured with the same amount of CPUs and memory as in our real experiments. For the CPULOAD benchmarks, we

set the `UtilizationModelFull` to simulate full CPU utilisation. We could not simulate the dirtying rate of the MEMLOAD benchmarks because CloudSim does not support this parameter. Nevertheless, we set `UtilizationModelFull` as the memory utilisation model to resemble the real executions as much as possible. Each `CloudLet` uses all resources allocated to the VMs. We simulated the load on the PMs by deploying a corresponding number of VMs, as we do for the real benchmarks (see Section VI-A).

c) *VM migration:* We simulated the VM migration in CloudSim by first extending the `VMSelectionPolicy` class so that only one VM is selected for migration, as we do in our benchmarks. Then, we extended the `VMAllocationPolicy` class to ensure that the selected VM is migrated to the desired target. The VM migration is issued in CloudSim at regular intervals determined by the `SCHEDULING_INTERVAL` parameter. We set this parameter to 40s that is the average time required by the power draw of a PM to stabilise, as explained in Section VI-A). Finally, we set for each simulation the `SIMULATION_LIMIT` parameter to the average execution time obtained in the real benchmark executions.

2) *Results:* We display in Table VI the MAE and NRMSE of the simulated energy consumption in GroudSim/DISSECT-CF and CloudSim compared to real measurements. We only present an aggregated the data centre level comparison, as CloudSim only provides energy simulation for the entire data centre. We only compare benchmark results that use live migration since CloudSim does not support non-live migration. We observe that our GroudSim/DISSECT-CF simulation reduces the NRMSE compared to CloudSim by 36.9% on the (m01, m02) machine set (i.e. 45.9% versus 9%), and by 42.4% on the (o1, o2) machine set (i.e. 68% versus 25.6%). We also notice that GroudSim/DISSECT-CF has a lower MAE for both data sets, showing a lower variance compared to CloudSim. We further observe that most errors in CloudSim are due to underestimation. Therefore, our better results stem not only from the improved accuracy in the CPU model, but also from considering the energy consumption of PM components such as networking and storage (ignored by CloudSim), and from a better VM migration model. Considering the memory dirtying rate parameter brings a significant improvement in the accuracy of the VM migration models in GroudSim/DISSECT-CF as shown in [8], since migrating a VM with a high memory dirtying rate can even double the migration time, that strongly impacts energy consumption.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we developed a new energy model for data centres energy consumption that considers CPU, network and storage hardware components. We evaluated its accuracy on traces collected from two different types of PMs in a private Cloud, showing a relative error lower than 18% on both data sets. Afterwards, we implemented our model in the user-side GroudSim simulator by exploiting its integration with

Simulator	Dataset	MAE live [kW h]	NRMSE live [%]
GroudSim / DISSECT-CF	(m01, m02)	0.0025	9
	(o1, o2)	0.0024	25.6
CloudSim	(m01, m02)	0.0190	45.9
	(o1, o2)	0.0075	68

TABLE VI: Simulation error comparison between GroudSim/DISSECT-CF and CloudSim.

the DISSECT-CF infrastructure simulator. We evaluated the accuracy of our implementation by comparing it with real measurements, showing a NRMSE between 8% and 22% for power prediction and between 8% and 25.6% for energy estimation. Finally, we compared the results obtained by our implementation with the CloudSim state-of-the-art simulator showing an improvement of at least 36.8% in energy modelling accuracy. In the future, we plan further improve the network and storage energy models in our simulator and use them for studying the effects of different energy-aware consolidation algorithms in modern virtualised data centres. We are further interested in validating our simulator with different real-world benchmarks such as TPC-C and SPECpower.

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